

NOTES

Biflavonyls Pigments from *Juniperus chinensis* (Cupressaceae)

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In continuation of our interest in the biflavonyl pigments of the cupressaceae, we wish to report the results of our investigations on the leaf extract of *Juniperus chinensis*. It constitutes an important timber producing species and is a leading source of wood for cabinet works, lead pencils and construction purposes¹. A volatile oil extracted from crushed juniper berries is the principal flavouring ingredient of gin. Several *Juniperus* species were found to contain tumour damaging lignans².

Swada³ in his studies on the distribution of biflavonyls in gymnosperm reported the presence of *kayaflavone* and *hinokiflavone* I in *Juniperus utilis* Koidz and *J. conferta* Parl.

The acetone extract of the powdered and dried leaves of *J. chinensis* on solvent fractionation and column chromatography (Magnesium silicate-Woelm) followed by preparative thin-layer chromatography using silica gel G (E. Merck) gave four homogeneous components.

The component m.p. 250° [α]_D²⁵—30° (Pyridine-methanol, 1 mg/ml) gave a hexaacetate m.p. 228–230° and a hexamethyl ether m.p. 217–220°, Mol. wt. 622 (mass). It was characterized as amentoflavone by NMR studies. Further support to its identity as amentoflavone was provided by comparison of NMR spectra of its acetate and methyl ether with those of

1. George H. N. Lawrence. Taxonomy of Vascular Plants, The Macmillan Company, New York, 1951, 307.
2. D. B. Fitzgerald, J. Hartwell and J. Leiter, *J. nat. cancer Inst.*, 1957, **18**, 83.
3. T. Swada, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1958, **78**, 1023.

authentic samples. IR-, UV-, and mass spectra were also identical with those of standard samples. The low melting point (250°) may be explainable on its being optically active⁴. The other compound m.p. 355° gave pentaacetate m.p. $237-240^{\circ}$ and a penta-methyl ether m.p. 260° . It was characterized as hinokiflavone II by NMR studies. The interflavonyl linkage from C4'-O-C8" as in I (previously assigned to hinokiflavone) was revised to C4'-O-C6" in II by solvent induced methoxy resonances⁵ of the pentamethyl ether.

The other two components were found to be apigenin and monomethyl ether of hinokiflavone. The former has been authenticated by the preparation of its derivatives and identical chromatographic and spectral behaviour with the authentic sample. The minor component has been characterized as monomethyl ether of hinokiflavone by a comparison of its R_f value with isocryptomerin. The methoxy group, however, cannot be oriented as three isomeric monomethyl ethers of hinokiflavone are reported.

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- b. K. K. Chexal, B. K. Handa, W. Rahman and N. Kawano, *Chem. und Ind.*, 1970, **28**.
- c. A. Pelter, R. Warren, N. Hameed, N. U. Khan, M. Ilyas and W. Rahman, *Phytochemistry*, 1970 (in press).
5. A. Pelter, R. Warren, J. N. Usmani, M. Ilyas and W. Rahman, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, **49**, 4259.